

Begin Your Open Science Journey:

BUILDING YOUR DIGITAL PRESENCE

BUILD YOUR DIGITAL CV:

- Register for an ORCID** at <https://orcid.org>. It provides a persistent digital identifier that distinguishes you from other researchers and supports automated linkages between you and your research activities.

TIP: Include your ORCID on all scholarly work: publications, datasets, software, presentations, posters, and the signature block of your emails.

- Enable automatic updates** from Crossref and DataCite in your ORCID profile. Follow the QR code on this postcard for a tutorial!
- Set a calendar reminder** every three months to check that all your work is connected and current in your ORCID profile.

Flip this card for more tips!

ENSURE YOUR RESEARCH PRODUCTS ARE LINKED TO YOUR PROFILE:

If you enabled automatic updates, your ORCID profile will automatically keep your publication, software, and data record up-to-date IF you:

- Include your ORCID** as well as your co-authors' ORCIDs on your publications.
- Upload your data and software** to discipline-appropriate repositories and include your ORCID, even if it is not required (just list each ORCID as close to the contributor name as possible). Find an overview of repository considerations and recommendations on the digital version of this postcard.

TIP: Ensure the digital identifiers (ex. DOI) for related work are included in your data/software record (or add them later). This includes the DOI of your paper citing the data or of the software used to analyze the data!

- Cite your data and software** in the references section of your publications to link your work, support reproducibility and transparency, AND get credit for your data and software. Learn how in the digital version of this postcard.

Digital version of this postcard w/ links and tutorials:

More resources for your Open Science Journey:

